

Synthesis of some 7,9-dimethyl-8-substituted pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]-pyrimidine and their antitubercular activity

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Abstract : A series of eight new 7,9-dimethyl-8-substituted pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidines (**4a-h**) have been synthesised starting from 3-substituted pentan-2,4-dione in three steps. These compounds have been characterized by NMR and mass spectroscopy and checked their antitubercular activity.

Keywords : Pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4-amine, synthesis, pentane-2,4-dione, cyanothioacetamide, chloroacetonitrile.

Introduction

Thienopyrimidines are a class of fused heterocycles, which are common sources for the development of new potential therapeutic agents. The formation of novel fused heterocycles is an important task for medicinal chemists from various points of view for the development of living things. Many condensed heterocyclic systems especially, when linked to a pyrimidine ring have attracted attention in the past few years as they are found in variety of natural products e.g. purines, pyrrolopyrimidines, pyridopyrimidines, pteridines. Among these heterocycles, the thienopyrimidine class is also of interest because some derivatives such as tiprinast has shown effective antiallergic¹⁻³ activity. In addition, antianaphilactic, antineoplastic⁴, antiatherosclerotic⁵, antibacterial^{6,7}, antidepressive^{8,9}, antidiabetic¹⁰, antihypertensive^{11,12}, antihistaminic^{13,14}, analgesic, anti-inflammatory^{15,16}, antiviral^{17,18}, spasmolytic¹⁹, antipyretic²⁰, anticonvulsant²¹, fungicidal²², antiplatelet²³ and other Central Nervous System (CNS) affecting²⁴ activities have been reported for certain thienopyrimidine derivatives.

Looking to the importance of thienopyrimidine moieties, we have synthesised some new thienopyrimidine moieties and screened for their antitubercular activities.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open glass capillary and are uncorrected. Progress of reaction was

monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel-G coated on aluminium plates (0.5 mm thickness, Merck) and spots were visualized under UV radiation. The newly synthesized compounds were purified by column chromatography and recrystallized. ¹H NMR spectra and ¹³C NMR spectra (selected compound) were recorded using CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆, as solvents and TMS as an internal reference and chemical shift value were expressed in δ_{ppm} on Bruker Avance-300 (300 MHz) and mass spectra on Ion trap Perkin-Elmer 1000 MS spectrometer. IR spectra of reported compounds were done using Thermo-Nicolat IR-200 spectrophotometer with KBr disk method.

General procedure for the synthesis of substituted pentane-2,4-dione (1a-h) : Sodium hydroxide (11 mmol) was dissolved in 3 ml of methanol at room temperature then chilled up to 0 °C in a ice bath. To resultant mixture acetyl acetone (10 mmol) was added over a period of 30 min at constant temperature 0 to 5 °C. Allowed the reaction mixture to come to room temperature and was added alkyl bromide (11 mmol) over a period of 30 min. Resultant mixture was refluxed for 1-3 h then allowed to stir at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated; residue obtained was purified by column chromatography to yield compound **1a-h**.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-substituted 2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile (2a-h) : To the solution of compound **1a-h** (10 mmol) in ethanol (5 ml) was

added cyanothioacetamide (10 mmol) was added followed by triethylamine (0.5 mmol) then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature then chilled at 0 °C. Solid was filtered and washed with chilled ethanol. Crude solid was purified by column chromatography to yield compound **2a-h**.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-substituted-3-amino-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carbonitrile (3a-h) : To a solution of compound **2a-h** (10 mmol) in methanol (25 ml) sodium methoxide (11 mmol) was added followed by chloroacetonitrile (11 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h. The resultant mixture was allowed to concentrate followed by water was added to the residue and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate, filtered and concentrated to give crude compound **3a-h**, which was purified by column chromatography to give purified compound **3a-h**.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-substituted-3-amino-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carbonitrile (4a-h) : To a solution of compound **3a-h** (10 mmol) in toluene (20 ml) was added to formamide (11 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was poured to on ice, aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with

brine, dried over sodium sulfate, filtered and concentrated to give crude product **4a-h**, which upon by column chromatography gave compound **4a-h** in pure state.

Results and discussion

The strategy adopted for the synthesis of these new condensed heterocyclic compounds involved successive building up of 7,9-dimethyl-8-substituted pyrido[3',2':4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4-amine by base induced alkylation of pentane-2,4-dione in methanol to yield corresponding 3-substituted pentane-2,4-dione, which upon condensation with cyanothioacetamide gave corresponding 5-substituted 2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile (**2a-h**). 5-Substituted 2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile (**2a-h**) when treated with chloroacetonitrile gave 5-substituted-3-amino-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carbonitrile (**3a-h**) followed by condensation with formamide in toluene at 110 °C yielded the target compounds **4a-h**.

The proton of pyrimidine ring appeared around δ 8.45 ppm as singlet, the protons of two methyl group appeared around δ 2–3 ppm as singlet and protons of amino group appeared around δ 6.5–8 ppm as singlet. This data is suggested that a basic skeleton of 7,9-dimethyl-8-substituted pyrido[3',2':4,5]thieno[3,2-d]pyrimidin-4-amine is present.

1a, R = Allyl; **1b**, R = Ethyl; **1c**, R = Benzyl; **1d**, R = Methyl; **1e**, R = Propyl; **1f**, R = Butyl; **1g**, R = *p*-Methylbenzyl; **1h**, R = *p*-Methoxybenzyl.

Reaction Scheme

Compound **1a** : 3-Allylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 58%, m.p. 156–158 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.19 (6H, s), 2.62 (2H, d), 3.31 (1H, t), 4.85 (1H, dd, *J* 16.7 Hz), 5.03 (1H, dd, *J* 10.3 Hz), 5.70 (1H, m); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1725 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 1645 (-C=C str. allylic), 2930 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 3090 (-C-H str. -C=CH₂), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1385, (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **1b** : 3-Ethylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 55.2%, m.p. 165–169 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.98 (3H, t), 1.95 (2H, m), 2.16 (6H, s), 3.25 (1H, t); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1730 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1430 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1390 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **1c** : 3-Benzylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 54.5%, m.p. 149–151 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.20 (6H, s), 3.10 (2H, d), 3.65 (IR, t), 7.12–7.21 (5H, m); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1725 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 2910 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1450 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1385 (-C-H ben. -CH), 1480 and 1590 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 695 and 740 (-C-H ben. mono substituted benzene).

Compound **1d** : 3-Methylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 60%, m.p. 143–145 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 1.36 (3H, d), 2.11 (6H, s), 3.40 (1H, q); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1735 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 2910 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1430 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1380 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **1e** : 3-Propylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 60.4%, m.p. 162–164 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.97 (3H, t), 1.35 (2H, m), 1.82 (2H, m), 2.11 (6H, s), 3.22 (1H, t); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1730 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1435 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1380 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **1f** : 3-Butylpentane-2,4-dione; yield 58%, m.p. 169–172 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.98 (3H, t), 1.30 (2H, m), 1.35 (2H, m), 1.85 (2H, m), 2.13 (6H, s), 3.23 (1H, t); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1730 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 2915 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1455 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1430 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1370 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **1g** : 3-(4-Methylbenzyl)pentane-2,4-dione; yield 61%, m.p. 158–163 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.30 (3H, s), 2.15 (6H, s), 3.10 (2H, d), 3.65 (1H, t), 7.02 (2H, d), 7.04 (2H, d); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1740 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 3030 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2940 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1450 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420

(-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1385 (-C-H ben. -CH), 1620 and 1510 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 800 (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

Compound **1h** : 3-(4-Methoxybenzyl)pentane-2,4-dione; yield 64%, m.p. 144–146 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.14 (6H, s), 3.75 (3H, s), 3.04 (2H, d), 3.70 (1H, t), 6.76 (2H, d), 7.05 (2H, d); IR (cm⁻¹) : 1745 (>C=O str. carbonyl group), 3040 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2930 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 1450 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1385 (-C-H ben. -CH), 1630 and 1515 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 810 (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

Compound **2a** : 5-Allyl-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 60%, m.p. 139–141 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.48 (3H, s), 2.49 (3H, s), 3.27 (2H, m), 4.86 (1H, d, *J* 16.8 Hz), 5.12 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz), 5.80 (1H, m); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3070 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2930 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2550 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2230 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1640 (-C=C- str. allylic), 1550 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1385 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **2b** : 5-Ethyl-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 56%, m.p. 134–136 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 1.30 (3H, t), 2.80 (2H, q), 2.47 (3H, s), 2.48 (3H, s); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3060 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2545 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2220 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1555 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **2c** : 5-Benzyl-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 54.7%, m.p. 129–133 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.48 (3H, s), 2.49 (3H, s), 3.85 (2H, s), 7.08–7.16 (5H, br); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3060 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2930 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2550 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2230 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1640 (-C=C- str. allylic), 1550 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1480 and 1590 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 695 and 740 (-C-H ben. mono substituted benzene).

Compound **2d** : 2-Mercapto-4,5,6-trimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 58%, m.p. 131–133 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.42 (3H, s), 2.43 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3030 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2540 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2210 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1555 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **2e** : 2-Mercapto-4,6-dimethyl-5-

propylnicotinonitrile; yield 64%, m.p. 138–139 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 1.01 (3H, t), 1.70 (2H, m), 2.47 (3H, s), 2.48 (3H, s), 2.65 (2H, t); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3060 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2560 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2220 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1565 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1460 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$).

Compound **2f** : 5-Butyl-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 57.5%, m.p. 142–144 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 1.00 (3H, t), 1.38 (2H, m), 1.62 (2H, m), 2.63 (3H, s), 2.46 (3H, s), 2.48 (2H, t); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3045 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2910 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2545 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2220 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1555 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1460 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1410 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$).

Compound **2g** : 5-(4-Methylbenzyl)-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 59%, m.p. 152–153 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 2.38 (3H, s), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.52 (3H, s), 3.65 (2H, s), 6.98–7.01 (4H, bs); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3030 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2540 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2210 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1555 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 810 (*p*-disubstituted benzene), 1620 and 1510 (-C=C- str. benzene ring).

Compound **2h** : 5-(4-Methoxybenzyl)-2-mercapto-4,6-dimethylnicotinonitrile; yield 62.3%, m.p. 142–145 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 2.45 (3H, s), 2.50 (3H, s), 3.60 (3H, s), 3.59 (2H, s), 6.70 (2H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3030 (-C-H str. aromatic), 2920 (-C-H str. aliphatic), 2850 (-C-H str. O- CH_3), 1050 and 1250 (-C-O str. ether group), 2540 (-S-H str. Ar-S-H), 2210 (-CN str. Ar-CN), 1555 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 810 (*p*-disubstituted benzene), 1620 and 1510 (-C=C- str. benzene ring).

Compound **3a** : 5-Allyl-3-amino-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 54%, m.p. 128–131 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 2.60 (3H, s), 2.67 (3H, s), 3.49 (2H, m), 4.77 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 17.0, *J*₂ 2.1 Hz), 4.89 (2H, bs), 5.07 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 9.9, *J*₂ 1.8 Hz), 5.93 (1H, m); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3390, 3460 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1645 (-C=C- str. allylic), 1465 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$), 1380 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **3b** : 3-Amino-5-ethyl-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 53.6%, m.p. 136–138 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 0.99 (3H, t), 2.45 (2H, q), 2.53 (3H, s), 2.58 (3H, s), 4.71 (2H, bs); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3390, 3450 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2220 (-CN str.), 2920 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2555 (-C-S str.), 1550 and 1610 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1460 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1410 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$).

Compound **3c** : 3-Amino-5-benzyl-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 56%, m.p. 145–147 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 2.60 (3H, s), 2.65 (3H, s), 4.00 (2H, s), 4.83 (2H, bs), 7.00–7.14 (5H, m); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3380, 3440 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1540 and 1610 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1465 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$), 1470 and 1595 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 690 and 745 (-C-H ben. mono substituted benzene).

Compound **3d** : 3-Amino-4,5,6-trimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 58.2%, m.p. 134–136 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 2.40 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s), 2.49 (3H, s), 4.65 (2H, bs); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3390, 3455 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$).

Compound **3e** : 3-Amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-propylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 58%, m.p. 131–133 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 1.00 (3H, t), 1.70 (2H, m), 2.55 (3H, s), 2.59 (2H, t), 2.60 (3H, s), 4.73 (2H, bs); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3375, 3445 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2920 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1465 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1420 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$).

Compound **3f** : 3-Amino-5-butyl-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 59%, m.p. 137–139 °C; ^1H NMR δ (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 1.10 (3H, t), 1.38 (2H, m), 1.65 (2H, m), 2.40 (2H, t), 2.51 (3H, s), 2.60 (3H, s), 4.84 (2H, bs); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3375, 3450 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2920 (-C-H str. Ar- CH_3), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1565 and 1610 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1470 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_2$), 1425 (-C-H ben. $-\text{CH}_3$).

Compound **3g** : 3-Amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-*p*-tolylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 58%, m.p. 138–

139 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.30 (3H, s), 2.60 (3H, s), 2.67 (3H, s), 3.90 (2H, s), 4.86 (2H, bs), 7.00–7.10 (4H, br); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3380, 3440 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1460 and 1585 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 810 (-C-H ben. *p*-substituted benzene).

Compound **3h** : 3-Amino-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4,6-dimethylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-2-carbonitrile; yield 63.5%, m.p. 145–148 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.61 (3H, s), 2.68 (3H, s), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.1 (2H, s), 4.84 (2H, bs), 6.80 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3380, 3440 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2230 (-CN str.), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1480 and 1590 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 815 (*p*-substituted benzene), 2860 (-C-H str. O-CH₃), 1055 and 1260 (-C-O str. ether group).

Compound **4a** : 7,9-Dimethyl-8-prop-2-en-1-ylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 52.8%, m.p. 201–203 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.51 (3H, s), 3.08 (3H, s), 3.58 (2H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz), 4.83 (1H, d, *J* 17.0 Hz), 5.20 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz), 6.0 (1H, m), 6.60 (2H, br), 8.45 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 271 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3390, 3460 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1640 (-C=C- str. allylic), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1380 (-C-H ben. -CH).

Compound **4b** : 8-Ethyl-7,9-dimethylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 51%, m.p. 209–212 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 1.50 (3H, t), 2.20 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s), 2.98 (2H, q), 6.70 (2H, bs), 8.50 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 259 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3380, 3450 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2900 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2540 (-C-S str.), 1550 and 1610 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1410 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **4c** : 8-Benzyl-7,9-dimethylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 52%, m.p. 232–234 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.10 (3H, s), 2.39 (3H, s), 3.75 (2H, s), 7.21 (5H, m), 7.61 (2H, bs), 8.60 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 321 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3390, 3450 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-

CH₃), 2560 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1620 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1470 and 1595 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 700 and 750 (-C-H ben. mono substituted benzene).

Compound **4d** : 7,8,9-Trimethylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 56%, m.p. 226–229 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.15 (3H, s), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.80 (3H, s), 7.60 (2H, bs), 8.55 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR δ (DMSO, 75 MHz) : 14.2, 17.5, 22.1, 107.2, 125.9, 132.1, 145.0, 152.9, 157.3, 159.3, 161.5, 163.4; MS : *m/z* 245 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3370, 3440 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2540 (-C-S str.), 1540 and 1610 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **4e** : 7,9-Dimethyl-8-propylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 56%, m.p. 214–216 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 1.00 (3H, t), 1.61 (2H, m), 2.22 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s), 3.25 (2H, t), 6.70 (2H, bs), 8.48 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 273 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3390, 3460 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1460 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1410 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **4f** : 8-Butyl-7,9-dimethylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 51.2%, m.p. 223–226 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 0.99 (3H, t), 1.40 (2H, m), 1.68 (2H, m), 2.23 (3H, s), 2.42 (3H, s), 3.21 (2H, t), 6.61 (2H, bs), 8.01 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 287 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3380, 3460 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2930 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2560 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1410 (-C-H ben. -CH₃).

Compound **4g** : 7,9-Dimethyl-8-(4-methylbenzyl)-pyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield 58.5%, m.p. 236–238 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.19 (3H, s), 2.41 (3H, s), 2.75 (3H, s), 3.90 (2H, s), 6.20 (2H, bs), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.49 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 8.56 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 335 {*M*+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3390, 3470 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. aromatic ring), 1465 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1420 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1460 and 1585 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 800 (-C-H ben. *p*-substituted benzene).

Compound **4h** : 8-(4-Methoxybenzyl)-7,9-dimethylpyrido[3',2' : 4,5]thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine; yield

59%, m.p. 243–245 °C; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 2.20 (3H, s), 2.48 (3H, s), 3.72 (3H, s), 3.85 (2H, s), 6.68 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.20 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.95 (2H, bs), 8.58 (1H, s); MS : *m/z* 351 {M+1}; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3390, 3465 (-N-H str. primary amine), 2910 (-C-H str. Ar-CH₃), 2550 (-C-S str.), 1560 and 1600 (-C=C- and -C=N- str. pyridine derivative), 1470 (-C-H ben. -CH₂), 1430 (-C-H ben. -CH₃), 1470 and 1590 (-C=C- str. benzene ring), 810 (*p*-substituted benzene), 2860 (-C-H str. O-CH₃), 1055 and 1260 (-C-O str. ether group).

Biological activity :

Eight compounds from the series were screened for their antitubercular activity. The standard strain *M. tuberculosis*, H₃₇ RV is tested with each new batch of medium. The recommended drug concentrations are 4 µg/ml for streptomycin, 0.2 µg/ml for isoniazide, 40 µg/ml for rifampicin and 2 µg/ml for ethambutol. Comparison of results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Antitubercular activity of compounds 4a-h

Sr. no.	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> MTCC 200 µg/ml
4a	50
4b	250
4c	100
4d	500
4e	100
4f	62.5
4g	250
4h	1000

The results of antitubercular activity show that compounds 4c and 4e are moderately active; 4a and 4f are excellently active against *M. tuberculosis*.

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